

The C is not silent - A Scoping Review of Critical Digital Literacy (CDL)

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1. Introduction: Critical Digital Literacy – A field in Continuous Expansion

Amidst a rapidly developing digital ecosystem redefining our economic, political, social and cultural systems, recent scholarship acknowledges that critical digital literacy (CDL) surpasses mere technical ability—it demands a capacity to question the power structures, biases, and ideologies shaping digital tools and platforms. The field is driven by a variety of actors such as teachers and educators, civil society, as well as scholars from a range of disciplines such as pedagogies, communication and information sciences or computer sciences and philosophy.

Without claiming completeness, this scoping review explores the broad and dynamic field laying out the components of CDL: literacy, digital literacy and critical digital literacy. In a first step it will look at the development of the term of “literacy” and the models of “autonomous” and “meaning making” as a social practice, before presenting the the debate around digital literacy and its expansion over the last three decades. Lastly, crucial elements of “critical digital literacy/ies”, namely centering self-reflexivity, teaching empathy, empowerment and inclusivity will be presented before finishing on important overlaps with digital divides research and questions on practical applications of CDL in teachings.

2. Digital Literacy: Definition and Clarification of Concepts

At the heart of **literacy** lies an **individual’s capacity to encode and decode information**. In its most traditional sense, this refers to the ability to read (decode) and write (encode) written language. However, these foundational skills extend naturally into other (digital) literacy domains. The «autonomous» approach to literacy translates western conceptions of literacy onto other contexts (see Street 2003). It consists of the of skills, tools, technique, or set of (mainly cognitive) competencies that are applied in diverse contexts and put of a range of uses and applications.

In 1997, Paul Gilster, a writer specializing in space technology introduced the term of the same name in his book “Digital Literacy” to describe the “ability to understand and use information in various forms and from multiple sources when presented via the computer” (cited by Fisseler p. 2).

Gilster identifies four core competencies in 1997 for the “digital” literacy: knowledge assembly, evaluating information content, searching the Internet, and navigating hypertext. In this model, the focus is on “**skills and techniques**”; that can be taught and learned and applied.

Critics of the autonomous model and its claim to neutrality, point out, that literacies need to be applied “with meaning” and are always embedded in context. The idea is that **there is not such a thing as “one literacy”** but many literacies that must be regarded as a practices infused and defined by power relations. Anthropologist and literacy scholar Brian Street notes that they are rooted in different worldviews and therefore also

“ideological” (Street, 2003, p. 2) . Consequently there are as **many different cultural ways of practicing (digital) literacy** as there are different cultural ways to read and write (Colin Lankshear & Michele Knobel, 2006).

Literary scholar Richard Lanham brings in some of the “context” by referring to “audiences” in his definition of digital literacy: “Digital literacy enables us to match the medium we use to the kind of information we are presenting and to the audience we are presenting it to.” To be digitally literate is understood as a skillset that includes “syntactical subtleties of the world” that are culturally grown and specific (Lanham 1995, p. 200 cited in Lankshear & Knobel, p.12).Education scholars Colin Lankshear and Michele Knobel stress the concept of “meaning making”: This is “mediated by texts that are produced, received, distributed, exchanged etc., via digital codification.”(Lankshear & Knobel, 2006, p. 17).

In literature, digital literacy is also categorized as a subset of “Metaliteracy” or a “special form” of media Literacy (Pötzsch, 2019, p. 222). The former brings reflection and shared content production into focus, urging learners to critically evaluate their roles as both consumers and creators. The multiliteracies framework (New London Group, 1996) adopts a socio-cultural approach and positions literacy as inherently multimodal—connecting visual, linguistic, spatial, and audio elements with meaning-making processes.

Component	Definition
Situated Practice	Immersion in experience and the utilization of available discourses, including those from the students' lifeworlds and simulations of the relationships to be found in workplaces and public spaces.
Overt Instruction	Systematic, analytic, and conscious understanding. In the case of multiliteracies, this requires the introduction of explicit metalanguages, which describe and interpret the Design elements of different modes of meaning.
Critical Framing	Interpreting the social and cultural context of particular Designs of meaning. This involves the students' standing back from what they are studying and viewing it critically in relation to its context.
Transformed Practice	Transfer in meaning-making practice, which puts the transformed meaning to work in other contexts or cultural sites.

Table 1: A Pedagogy of Multiliteracies (New London Group, 1996, p. 88)

(framework cited in:(Drewry et al., 2019, p.62)

Fisseler (2024) proposes a pedagogical framework for **digital accessibility literacy**, integrating awareness, technical standards, inclusive design practices, and continuous feedback within CDL pedagogy. It uses the classical literacy strands of encoding and decoding as a starting point to then develop his model of digital accessibility literacy, integrating a more **inclusive and transformative approach**:

1. Encoding (creating digital accessibility)
 - Understanding and promoting digital accessibility: Raising awareness, fostering a culture of digital accessibility and inclusion.

- Creating accessible content: Understanding and applying design principles, adhering to technical standards.
 - Use and develop accessible technologies: use software and technologies and develop innovative solutions
2. Decoding (understanding and using digital accessibility)
- Interpreting accessible digital content: using and understanding accessible presentation, enabling access to information
 - Obtain and use feedback: Obtaining feedback from users, using feedback for adaptations, and making adaptations
 - Develop inclusive solutions: Using knowledge, feedback, and data to improve digital accessibility, developing and implementing strategies (Fisseler, p. 2)

The **European Digital Competence framework (Digcomp)**, integrated in [ESCO](#) gives a more standardized approach to digital literacy that is needed for formulating and implementing policy. It distinguishes the dimensions of problem-solving, communication, content creation, information management, and online safety—(EU; Carretero Gomez, S., Vuorikari, R. and Punie, Y., 2017). The EU framework, critics argue, falls short of addressing political and ethical dimensions. Media scholar Holger Pötsch stresses the critical aspect of awareness for environmental impacts, but misses the inclusion of alternative media and “economic frames predisposing affordances and possible use of commercial products” (Pötsch, 2019, p. 223).

Analyzing and mitigating corporate governance is what Pötsch and others see as an essential part of “critical” digital literacy.

Ever since these first conceptualizations three decades ago, the field in digital literacy is constantly growing. Most recently, breakthroughs in generative AI and LLMs technology as well as its applications and narratives, **data literacy or AI literacy** expand the field of digital literacy (Buolamwini, 2023; Hannigan et al., 2024; Roe et al., 2025)

Roe, Furze & Perkins (2025) introduce the metaphor of *digital plastic* to describe GenAI content, warning against digital misinformation bloat and advocating for *Critical AI Literacy* within educational strategies (Roe et al., 2025). Other authors introduce ways to use LLMs while navigating risks, posed by “botshit”. I.e. introduce a typology framework that orients how chatbots can be used based on two dimensions: response veracity verifiability and response veracity importance. The framework identifies four modes of chatbot work (authenticated, autonomous, automated, and augmented) with a botshit-related risk (ignorance, miscalibration, routinization, and black boxing) ((Hannigan et al., 2024).

In *Unmasking AI*, computer scientist Joy Buolamwini chronicles how facial recognition systems, developed by largely homogenous teams using biased datasets, systematically misidentify women and people of color. By advocating for transparency, fairness, and inclusive design, she embodies CDL in practice: confronting technological oppression with informed critique and civic engagement (Buolamwini, 2023).

AI education scholars Kathleen Kennedy and Anuj Gupta develop the AI & Data Acumen Learning Outcomes Framework drawing from and providing an overview over already existing AI literacy frameworks (ibid. p.185). They distinguish Core Principles for AI Integration in Higher Education: Human Agency, Academic Freedom, Transparency, Ethics, Inclusivity and lastly Critical Thinking (ibid., table 3, p. 189), with the latter being the distinct element in CDL, we are turning to next.

3. Including the “Critical” in Digital Literacies

Critical Thinking, by the widely cited and agreed upon definition by Bloom refers to **knowledge** (recall of ideas), **comprehension** (demonstrating understanding of ideas), **application** (putting ideas into practice), **analysis** (contrasting and relating ideas), **synthesis** (combining ideas), and **evaluation** (judging ideas through criteria) (Bloom, cited in: Lee et al., 2025, p. 5). For digital literacy to incorporate critical thinking, these six dimensions would need to be integrated into Critical Digital Literacy (CDL) curricula.

Literature around critical digital literacy uses the **dichotomy of “Bildung” and “Ausbildung”** to refer to the different orientations of education. While the former encompasses the Humboldtian idea of critical thinking where “the individual gradually matures through self-reflective engagement with itself and its surroundings” (Pötzsch, 2019, p. 223), and “refers to societal aspects and identity development” (Löfving, 2023, p. 146), while the latter constitute mere “tools” designed for labor market qualification (Pötzsch, 2019, p. 223). While digital literacy may often be understood as an Ausbildung, the **critical component in CDL stress the importance of “Bildung” in the curricula.**

Other authors point out that centering the **impacts** a new digital technology will have on **marginalized people** is an essential part of CDL. As new technology is never neutral but favors certain groups while hurting others, critical thinking also covers thinking about the consequences that result from new technology. This is central in digital accessibility studies, where analyzing the implications technologies have for marginalized groups such as people with a disability is central (Fisseler, 2024, p. 2). Fisseler is advocating for understanding questions of accessibility and inclusion not only as a technical skill set, but a socio-technological challenge, where **CDL includes teaching values such as “empathy”.**

Holger Pötzsch (2019) asserts that CDL must foster “awareness for and knowledge about the practices and **logics of exploitation, commodification, and profit maximisation underlying contemporary techno-capitalism**” (Pötzsch, 2019, p.226). The logics of exploitation refer to the exploitation of labor and highly problematic working conditions in the digital economy, but also to the exploitation of rare earths and environmental risks posed by eWaste, or “AI plastic”. Teaching “empathy” in this context can also include raising awareness on detrimental damages on climate and the planet or exposing working conditions of “data workers” in the field of data annotation or content moderation (Ranta, 2024) or persisting colonial structures in the exploitation of labor and environment by the digital industry (Posada, 2021). Research methodologies centering data workers themselves unveil the hidden sides of AI and data work (for working conditions of content moderators, see also Roberts, 2019).

CDL also includes the element of **empowering people or users for using and applying digital media technologies for social change**. Critical digital literacy scholar Allan Luke define CDL as "naming and renaming the world, seeing its patterns, designs and complexities, and developing the capacity to redesign and reshape it" (2014, 29, cited in: (Pötzsch, 2019, p. 223). The call to action as a form of critical pedagogy and aim of teaching is also found in the media literacy model for an engaged citizen by Paul Mihailidis (Mihailidis, 2014). Media literacy scholar Jad Melki point to Western centered perspectives in the field and sheds light on emancipatory pedagogies developed for and with marginalized communities and people in postcolonial countries (Melki, 2025).

Lastly, with a focus on addressing and transforming societal power structures, CDL can be regarded as a framework to tackle **growing inequalities conceptualized in digital divides scholarship**. Literature distinguishes here between between access, skills/competences for use and outcomes of technologies (Ragnedda, 2018, p.1). In accordance with critical AI literacies, digital divide scholars have expanded the three level divides approach, adding the fourth level, or next level of digital divides (McCarthy, 2016, p. 1133). The scholarship around digital divides presents one of many bodies of literature that can help to frame, show urgency and give direction of critical digital literacy in practice for social cohesion, the protection of democratic institutions and practices as well as the protection of planetary resources.

4. CDL in Practice: Pedagogical Frameworks and Tools

Recent issues of the Nordic Journal of Digital Literacy explore how educators implement DL in practice. Löfving (2023) finds that Swedish teachers often focus on technical skills and responsible use, but rarely integrate **democratic ideals or critical resistance contributions** —an outcome of regulatory and curricular constraints. Her finding is important to expand on advocacy strategies that equip institutions and teachers with the necessary equipment and hours to incorporate these aspects of "Bildung" as part of Digital Literacy Education polices.

Drawing also from observations by Lewthwaite and Sloan, Educational technologist scholar Björn Fisseler finds that in practice, there is little interdisciplinarity or exchange when it comes to digital accessibility pedagogies (Fisseler, 2024). Similarly, critical digital literacy needs can profit from **dynamic and interdisciplinary exchange**, along a socio-technological framework balancing technical skills, teachings empathy and political economies behind technologies.

A recurring question for CDL in practice is if and how to engage and include digital technologies in teachings. Pötzsch distinguishes **three dimensions to teach CDL**: 1) the use of and reflection about alternative non-commercial products serving similar functions as their corporate counterparts, 2) direction of attention to the history of 'new' technologies and contemporary data activism and its political practices, and 3) the increased use in class of cultural expressions that have issues of power, surveillance, and exploitation in digital domains as their explicit themes.

There are several other fields that bring together approaches in pedagogies around digital literacy:

- **Lateral Reading:** The *Critical Digital Literacy Education Guide* emphasizes connecting historical media manipulation—such as wartime propaganda and immigration-era misinformation—to modern digital environments influenced by bots and trolls. The guide calls for skills like source evaluation, emotional analysis, fact-checking, and algorithmic awareness—all within a civic education framework (Historica Canada, 2020).
- **Multimodal Content Creation:** Student-produced podcasts, videos, and infographics promote reflection and critical engagement. This dimension of CDL education also fosters student’s creativity and can empower them to engage in small tech initiatives. This dimension is drawing from the metaliteracies framework.
- **Professional Development:** Scandinavian studies signal that teacher trainings are essential to integrating CDL meaningfully. Others argue, that teachers do not necessitate additional training, but rather skills from the humanities (close reading, interpretation in context, in-depth understanding, and critical reflection) that can counter-balance the “technologically-facilitated push towards hyper-attention”(Pötzsch, 2019, p. 225). Löfving argues that “digital competence among teachers, is both subject-specific and generic, requiring continual reinterpretation.”
- **Critical AI Literacies:** In the field of critical AI studies, addressing technology but also narratives surrounding it, several research institutions, activist networks and civil society organizations provide groundbreaking work to inform CDL and CAIL. The Algorithmic Justice League, founded by Joy Buolamwini or the Distributed AI Research Institute (DAIR), founded by Timnit Gebru are research institution and sites of knowledge production that can also serve as an important resource for creating critical digital literacy curricula. Educamint is a website providing multiple tools and resources to integrate into classes, for education of different ages. For example, the project “Algorithmen in unserem Alltag”, elaborated [by Siemens Stiftung and iRights Initiative](#) provides learning packages.

5. Conclusion: Addressing the Ambivalences in Digital Literacies

Critical digital literacy is an evolving, interdisciplinary field unfolding rapidly and in convergence with academia, pedagogical practice, civil society and policy makers. It redefines literacy from technical fluency to political and ethical agency—challenging all types of students to question how platforms, algorithms, and media narratives not only shape their lives but also impact most vulnerable groups and the planet.

In practices, the literature sketches out the ambivalence in recognizing the need to teach skillsets for the evolving technological datafied environment as part of an “Ausbildung” responding to need to match the requirements of the current job market while not losing track (and resources for research and teaching) of “Bildung”, that also encompasses humanities or practical disciplines such as literature, the arts, or music. These constitute important elements against “hyper attention, fragmentation and commodification”(Pötzsch, 2019, p. 228) and therefore continue to be essential – especially in CDL curricula.

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